

Microcalcification detection with morphological operations and watershed segmentation

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Abstract— Mammography is the main exam used for breast cancer early detection, allowing to find suspicious structures, such as microcalcifications, small calcium deposits that may be associated with breast cancer. Research in digital image processing in segmentation techniques aims to divide the image into regions based on specific characteristics to facilitate the visualization of structures and use them in classification algorithms. Given the challenge in microcalcification detection, which often appear as small bright spots and can be easily misinterpreted as noise, the goal of this work is to apply watershed segmentation in mammograms to segment microcalcifications, using morphological operators to detect internal and external markers and restrain the segmentation process. After applying different denoising methods, the marker detection step performs the h-maxima operation using a disk-shaped structuring element with a radius of 3 pixels and an iterative threshold to binarize the result. The outcomes of the marker-controlled watershed segmentation were labeled as true or false positives based on annotation provided by the image database. The comparison of the mean and standard deviation of evaluation metrics across different denoising techniques suggests that an appropriate combination between h-maxima operation, thresholding, and noise reduction method can be used for the detection and segmentation of suspicious objects with microcalcification characteristics.

Keywords — *Segmentation, Watershed, Microcalcification, Mammography.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the second most diagnosed type of cancer worldwide, reaching about 73,610 new cases in 2023 in Brazil, that means 66.54 cases for each 100,000 women. In 2020, the number of deaths has reached 17,825, which means 16.47 deaths for each 100,000 women. Considering the concern in breast cancer control, the Brazilian Ministry of Health recommends that women between ages 50 and 69 have screening mammograms every two years. A mammogram is a radiographic exam performed on a mammograph and can detect breast alterations before the appearance of cancer-related symptoms, allowing early treatment [1–3].

Mammographic findings can appear in different shapes, sizes, and densities and are associated with breast cancer according to these characteristics. Microcalcifications, a mammographic finding type, are composed of small calcium

deposits with a size smaller than 1 mm and different shapes. The presence of microcalcifications in a mammogram might mean a suspicion of breast cancer [4].

Given the importance of early detection for the treatment of women with breast cancer, several studies have been carried out to promote accurate detection with mammography. In this scenario, computational systems are a great ally, especially in segmentation area, a processing capable of separating structures of interest, such as microcalcifications, from the rest of the image. Segmentation, when performed correctly, helps in the detection of lesions, allowing radiologists to visualize structures that could go unnoticed [5–7].

One of the techniques used in microcalcification segmentation is watershed segmentation. In watershed, the image is viewed from a topography view, represented by three coordinates: two spatial coordinates and one regarding the gray level intensity. The watershed lines are the object's boundary and are the points to be extracted in segmentation [5, 7].

The main challenge in watershed segmentation is avoiding oversegmentation, that means the detection of a great number of meaningless objects. This problem occurs due to noise presented in the image, which causes the existence of a lot of regional minima and forms many watersheds. To solve this problem, it is possible to use preprocessing, applying denoising to reduce existing noise, or use some techniques to limit the number of regional minima in which watershed will be applied, using markers obtained from the image features [5, 7, 8].

The aim of this work is to segment microcalcifications in mammograms using watershed segmentation. Microcalcification often appears as small bright spots in image, so, the challenge consists in the detection of suspicious regions that will be used as markers in the segmentation process.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Database

The mammographic images used in this work are from the image database INbreast in DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) format. The images were acquired in São João Hospital Center in Porto, Portugal, between April, 2008 and July, 2010 using a FFDM (Full Field Digital Mammography) mammograph. The images have 12 bits of resolution and pixel size of 70 μm . The annotations were available in XML (Extensible Markup Language) and the ground truth was obtained by the reconstruction of the objects using their correspondent points [9].

A total of 1134 regions of interest (ROIs) with a size of 100 \times 100 pixels containing at least 4 microcalcifications in the ground truth were extracted from 65 images. These ROIs were processed with a Python algorithm developed for denoising, detection, and segmentation of microcalcifications. Furthermore, the detected regions were compared with the ground truth and some metrics were calculated to analyze the performance of the detection and segmentation method. Examples of ROIs used in this work are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Regions of interest with microcalcifications.

B. Detection of microcalcifications

The detection step of the algorithm is design to find small bright objects in the image that could indicate microcalcifications. This characteristic appears in the regional maximum of an image, that is, a connected component with external boundary pixels strictly less than the object intensity value. Unfortunately, this pattern also appears in random noise, which causes difficulty in distinguishing between noise and suspicious objects [10].

The noise in mammographic images is the main cause of oversegmentation in microcalcification segmentation problems. Considering this, the first step in the detection algorithm is denoising the image, in this case, filtering each ROI using two different methods: Wiener filter and wavelet transform [5, 11].

The Wiener filter is a denoising method in the frequency domain to minimize the mean square error between the original and the filtered images. Defining the mask size, in this work, a 3 \times 3 mask, the filter is capable of blurring different contents in the image [5, 12].

Wavelet transform divides the image into four subimages, or coefficients, when set to one decomposition level, and can be used as a denoising method when combined with thresholding. In this work, using the function *Coiflets5*, the wavelet transform was applied to the original images, and a threshold defined by the image variance and the Rayleigh distribution was used for thresholding the diagonal, vertical, and horizontal coefficients. The filtered image results from the inverse wavelet transform with the three modified coefficients and the approximation subimage [5, 12, 13].

After denoising, the filtered images were processed with morphological operators to detect regional maximum with size and intensity defined by the structuring element and the selected method. The h-maxima operation was chosen considering its capacity to extract regions according to the object's size and the difference between the pixel intensity and its neighborhood [10].

The h-maxima image is obtained using the morphological reconstruction by dilation of an image f by $f-h$. The value of h is the smallest variation between the intensity of the pixel and its neighborhood. The image with the objects that represents the regional maxima results from thresholding the h-convex image, which consists in the difference between h-maxima and the original image. In this work, after empirical testing, the value of h was set as 0.04, and the structuring element used in the morphological operation had the shape of a disk with 3 pixels as radius [10, 14].

The internal markers for the watershed segmentation were obtained from the binarization of the h-convex image using an iterative thresholding. Applying different thresholds, starting from the maximum to the minimum intensity value in image, allows to choose the one that results in a predetermined number of connected components. Considering the 100 \times 100 size of the ROIs, the iterative thresholding limited the number of markers up to 50 objects. The markers with an area greater than 250 pixels were eliminated from the binary images to prevent oversegmentation in the results [6, 14].

The external marker, related to the background of the image, is obtained from the watershed lines of the watershed segmentation applied to a filtered version of the image. This filtered image results from inversion of the image after morphological closing and opening of the ROI. The final version of the markers is the combination of the internal marker, referring to the objects, and the external marker, obtained from the background of the regions [7, 10, 14].

C. Watershed segmentation

The watershed segmentation is applied in the morphological gradient of the original image using the markers to restrict the number and expansion of regions in segmentation. The morphological gradient consists in the difference between the eroded and dilated versions of image using a 3 \times 3 structuring element [5, 10].

The results of watershed segmentation are connected regions delimited by the watershed lines, which represent the border of the regions. Segmented objects with an area smaller than 4 pixels and greater than 250 pixels were considered false positives and eliminated from the results.

D. Evaluation

The segmented results were compared with the ground truth and classified as true or false positives according to overlapping pixels of each object. Each result that overlaps a ground truth was verified, and two metrics based on the number of pixels in each object were calculated.

The Overlap Value (OV) and Overlap Fraction (OF) make use of the number of pixels in intersection and union between the ground truth A and the object B and the number of pixels of the ground truth to verify the similarity between the regions. These metrics were calculated using the following equations [7].

$$OV = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (1)$$

$$OF = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A|} \quad (2)$$

In this work, segmented objects were classified as a true positive if the calculated OV was greater than 0.1 or the OF was equal to 1. The objects in the ground truth that were not detected were considered false negatives. After this, the metrics described in Table 1 were calculated to evaluate the performance of the segmentation method in each ROI.

TABLE 1. Metrics for performance evaluation.

Metric	Description
Number of objects	Number of objects in segmentation result
True positives	Number of objects classified as true positives
False positives	Number of objects classified as false positives
False negatives	Number of objects classified as false negatives
Sensitivity	$\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
Accuracy	$\frac{TP}{TP+FP+FN}$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At first, after denoising the images, 2268 filtered ROIs were generated and went through the process of microcalcification detection. After segmentation, the watershed lines were superimposed in each ROI according to

the classification of the segmented objects. In Fig. 2, the borders marked in green are true positive cases; in red, the objects are false positives; and in yellow, the false negative regions according to the ground truth.

Fig. 2. Microcalcification segmentation.

The results indicate that low contrast between microcalcification and background is the main cause of false negatives in h-maxima detection. This could be improved by using denoising and enhancement techniques to change the contrast between the regions. Other solutions are adjustments in h-maxima parameters and thresholding method, however, these approaches often increase both true and false positive objects, requiring additional effort for object classification.

Considering that watershed segmentation analyzes the intensity of pixels in object and background, the similarity between pixels of the same region affects the shape of the segmented object. That said, object blurring might be the

main cause of results with irregular shapes, partial detection, or divided objects.

Besides that, considering the metrics described, Table 2 analyzes the results from each denoising method using the mean and standard deviation of the results from each ROI. This comparison suggests that the denoising method has a major role in microcalcification detection.

TABLE 2. Mean and standard deviation (SD) of the metrics calculated for each ROI.

Metric	Wiener		Wavelet	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
True positives	5.82	3.43	6.33	3.23
False negatives	1.29	1.49	0.94	1.33
False positives	16.17	4.08	17.62	3.82
Number of objects	30.66	4.85	31.58	4.21
Sensitivity (%)	80.14	23.48	87.20	17.26
Precision (%)	25.97	13.52	26.14	11.47
Accuracy (%)	24.76	13.05	25.24	11.08

The results indicate that detection performed in ROIs filtered with wavelet transform was able to find more objects than the ones filtered with Wiener, increasing the number of true positives and, consequently, the value for sensitivity. The similar values for precision and accuracy of both denoising techniques suggest that there is a proportion of right and wrong objects in the detection method.

The h-maxima evaluates the difference of intensity between the region delimited by the structuring element and its neighbors. Therefore, denoising the image causes changes in regional maxima and border of objects, allowing h-maxima to detect different regions. Wiener filter is more powerful in deblurring the image than wavelet transform, increasing the possibility of missing low contrast objects.

IV. CONCLUSION

The segmentation of images is a recurrent theme in research about digital image processing and can play an important role in some applications. The detection and segmentation of microcalcifications could facilitate visualization of these structures by a radiologist and help in breast cancer early detection. In addition, segmented objects are fundamental to work with classification algorithms to separate regions in different categories.

In this work, microcalcification detection using morphological operators investigates suspicious objects in regions of interest of size 100×100 pixels according to the difference of intensity between a pixel and its neighborhood. The results indicate that h-maxima operator can detect most of regional maxima in image and can be used as a marker definition method in watershed segmentation.

The watershed technique uses markers to restrain the segmentation. These markers are directly related to sensitivity

and precision. The appropriate method for marker definition needs to achieve an acceptable proportion of true and false positives. In this case, segmentation could be improved by changing the structuring element size, the difference of intensity between regions, and the threshold method. However, it is important to emphasize that the detection of many regions may cause oversegmentation in image, increasing the number of false positives.

Changing the denoising method, different regions were segmented due to the blurring capacity of each technique. It confirms the importance of applying pre-processing methods to improve the noise ratio and contrast of the original image.

Further work intends to improve marker selection and segmentation results using neural networks for classification. In classification problems, different features are used to predict if a segmented object is a microcalcification. These features are related to intensity, texture, and shape of objects and their similarity with image background [6].

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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